

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**A SHORT REVIEW OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND
MACHINE LEARNING ON DRUG DISCOVERY IN THE
PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY****Miss. Avula Buela¹, Mr. V. S. Chandrasekaran^{2*}, Dr. K. Venugopal³**¹Final year B Pharmacy, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati – 517 506.²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Biotechnology, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati – 517 506.³Professor and Principal, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati – 517 506.**Abstract:**

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning are transforming the pharmaceutical industry by enhancing efficiency in drug discovery, clinical trials, and personalized medicine. Originating from concepts established in the mid-20th century, Artificial Intelligence simulates human intelligence to process and analyze vast datasets, facilitating the identification of drug targets and optimizing compound screening. Key goals include the development of expert systems that emulate human decision-making and the application of Machine Learning algorithms to improve predictive accuracy in various domains, including healthcare. Recent advancements such as generative AI, multimodal AI, and edge computing are further reshaping the landscape, while challenges like data privacy and integration persist. The pharmaceutical sector increasingly employs Artificial Intelligence to streamline R&D processes, reduce costs, and improve market strategies, with projections indicating a rapid market growth for AI applications in this field. By 2028, the market for AI in pharmaceuticals is anticipated to reach \$5.62 billion, reflecting a CAGR of 28.5%. In conclusion, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning promise to enhance drug development efficiency and patient outcomes, though careful management of ethical concerns and data privacy will be crucial for their successful implementation.

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence, Machine learning, Drug discovery, Personalized medicine, Clinical trials, pharma marketing, Data privacy.*

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Please cite this article in press Avula Buela et al., A Short Review Of Artificial Intelligence And Machine Learning On Drug Discovery In The Pharmaceutical Industry., *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2024; 11 (10).

1. INTRODUCTION:

Artificial Intelligence refers to the simulation of human intelligence in machines that are programmed to think and perform tasks like humans. Artificial Intelligence is sometimes described as a technology that enables machines to mimic a variety of intricate human talents (1,2). The idea of Artificial Intelligence was first put up in 1956 during a meeting organized by Marvin Minsky and John McCarthy.

A modern technology-based system called artificial intelligence (AI) uses advanced tools, networking, and technologies to simulate human intelligence. It consists of hardware and software which can draw conclusions from the data provided and acts independently. The usage of digitalization in the pharmaceutical industry has undergone significant development.

Computers are used in artificial intelligence to simulate intelligent decision-making. The most essential subset of AI named as machine learning (ML), is commonly confused with AI. The term "machine learning" refers to the capacity to continuously statistically understand data without any explicit programming. The use of AI could significantly change the speed and scope of drug discovery today (3,4).

1. GOALS OF AI:

- **Developing Expert Systems:** The primary goal is the development of automated systems with intelligent behavior, to guide and advise individuals to help them make the best judgments possible.
- **Developing Human-like Intelligence in Computers:** AI aims to replicate human cognitive patterns, allowing computers to act like people and make wise judgments, particularly in challenging and complicated settings. Algorithms are crucial for automating tasks and reducing the stress on workers.
- **Applications in a Variety of Domains:** AI has uses in a variety of disciplines, including computer science, cognitive science, statistics, psychology, engineering, ethics, the natural sciences, medicine, space technology, logic, and linguistics, among others.
- **Applications in Computer Science:** Several mechanisms, such as Search and Optimization, Logic, Control Theory, Language Analysis, Neural Networks, Classifiers, Statistical Learning Methods, and Probabilistic Methods for Uncertain Reasoning, are developed with

the help of AI to address a wide range of difficult problems in the field of computer science.

A branch of artificial intelligence and computer science called machine learning (ML) enables systems to automatically learn from experience and interpret it better. ML is incredibly helpful for managing suppliers and paperwork, organizing the transfer of commodities, and predicting likely supplier demand. With the advent of contemporary AI techniques, pharmaceuticals, and biomedical science now have access to extremely trustworthy computational approaches. Artificial intelligence (AI) simulates human intelligence in computer models to improve or mimic human performance (4,5).

Drug development is a procedure that is exceedingly expensive, time-consuming, and subject to several formalities in the pharmaceutical industry. An important change in the success rate of drug development has been the introduction of artificial intelligence (AI), deep learning (DL), machine learning (ML), and computational chemistry. In the recent decade, there has been a tremendous increase in the number of pharmaceutical companies and startups employing AI in drug research and development.

3. MACHINE LEARNING:

Computer algorithms that provide computers the ability to automatically learn and improve from experience are the subject of the study known as machine learning. The majority of people consider it to be a branch of artificial intelligence. The systems' ability to learn from experience and improve through the use of machine learning algorithms. Making decisions is made possible by machine learning algorithms.

3.1 Machine learning description:

It is built on an AI application that teaches fundamentally algorithms or computer programs the capacity to familiarize automatically with a task and also build expertise without programming. The ability of computer programs to approach data and use it for learning is improved by it. To redact advancements, a system needs programmers to write and review appropriately (6,7,8).

3.2 Types of machine learning:

There are basically three distinct categories of machine learning. These are they.

i. Supervised learning:

When the data consists of input variables and output target values, supervised learning is used. The algorithm learns how to translate the input function to the output function. The goal is to establish the risk generator and to seek trials in clinic optimization.

ii. Unsupervised learning:

This is the inverse of supervised learning. This means unsupervised learning is used when the data is only accessible as an input and there is no corresponding output variable. Clustering is one of the most common types of unsupervised algorithms. This technique discovers intrinsic groups in data

and then uses them to predict output for unknown inputs. Predicting customer purchase behaviour is an example of this strategy.

iii. Reinforcement learning:

It is similar to the unsupervised learning method. It is the Machine Learning instruction to build a decision order. A game-like situation is presented to an artificial intelligence.

Examples: 1. Teaching agents to play computer games.

2. Doing robotics tasks with a specific objective in mind.

Figure 1: Types of Machine Learning

4. MANAGEMENT OF NETWORKS USING AI / ML:

Many challenges in network administration call for an immediate response. To solve these urgent issues, AI is being applied in four different areas of network administration. As follows:

- Traffic control,
- Performance evaluation,
- Capacity planning
- Security surveillance

Of all the AI techniques, ML is proven to be the most helpful in solving issues in the majority of these situations. AI is sophisticated enough to consider a wide range of potential fixes for several problems.

Examples include:

- Random optimization,
- Beam search,
- Simulated annealing,
- Blind hill climbing, and
- Optimization searches
- Calculations based on evolution
- Gene expression programming,
- Genetic programming,
- Genetic algorithms

Particle swarm optimization was inspired by the behavior of flocks of animals.

Logic:

It can be used for expressing knowledge and solving problems, but it can also be used for other issues. For examples:

- The planning process in the SatPlan algorithm
- Probabilistic approaches to reasoning under uncertainty
- Case-based reasoning,
- AI research
- Logic of propositions

- uses truth-related operations like "or" and "not"
- Primate logic
- Predicates,
- Fuzzy,
- Default Logics,
- Non-Monotonic Logics,
- Propositional Logic,
- Adds Quantifiers,
- Default reasoning,
- The frame problem,
- Circumscription,
- The closed world assumption,
- Abduction
- The logic of description
- Displaying classes and relations

5. CURRENT SCENARIO OF MACHINE LEARNING IN PHARMACEUTICAL SECTOR:

Several latest trends in AI and machine learning are shaping industries and influencing their sustainability. For aspiring tech professionals, understanding and harnessing the possibilities presented by these transformative technologies is both crucial and thrilling (9,10,11).

5.1 Generative AI:

Generative AI is anticipated to experience further advancements due to increased funding expectations. This technology, renowned for its ability to generate **human-like text, videos, images, and speech, boasts user-friendly features, contributing to its widespread acceptance.** The next wave of research is expected to focus on seamlessly integrating generative AI with various platforms. The technology's quantitative and qualitative contributions are anticipated to drive significant growth for businesses, earning praise from mainstream media.

Figure 2. Top Machine Learning Trends

5.2 Multimodal AI:

Multimodal AI, capable of combining numeric text, data, images, and videos, is gaining traction for its ability to enhance application performance and contextual awareness. Benefits include **improved user interaction in applications like virtual assistants, and the integration of text, visual, and speech inputs.** Cross-modal learning, along with enhanced creativity and innovation, further propels the popularity of multimodal AI.

5.3 Edge Computing:

Edge Computing, integrated into distributed computing frameworks, accelerates data processing by bringing it closer to the data sources. This real-time local processing minimizes bandwidth and latency, significantly impacting remote workspace facilities. Deep Learning, mimicking the human brain with multiple processing layers, is exponentially gaining popularity. Businesses leverage deep learning in product development, ranging from autonomous driving cars to personalized experiences on e-commerce and OTT platforms.

5.4 Explainable AI:

Explainable AI addresses the growing reliance on AI by providing transparency and reasoning behind its judgments. Bridging the gap between humans and AI, this approach is crucial for enhancing decision-

making accuracy in industries like healthcare and human resources. No-code Machine Learning allows model building and deployment through a simple drag-and-drop interface reducing the need for extensive programming. This time and cost-efficient approach offer speed and flexibility without requiring high technical expertise.

N-shot learning employs advanced techniques to achieve the desired output with minimal input data, eliminating the need for extensive databases or lengthy prompts. Common applications **include facial recognition, image, and text classification.**

5.5 Metaverses:

Metaverses, akin to alternate universes, enable the simultaneous execution of diverse tasks such as business operations, establishing virtual lives, and generating income. Their high growth potential positions them as a significant trend in recent machine learning developments. The global metaverse market size was estimated to be USD 65.5 billion in 2022. It is projected to experience a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of **41.6% from 2023 to 2030.** Quantum Computing addresses complex problems in AI by leveraging principles of quantum mechanics. This trend is expected to offer breakthroughs in machine learning algorithms and optimization problems.

5.6 Digital Twins:

Digital Twins emerging as a compelling AI offering, involves creating digital replicas of real-world assets. Businesses and governments benefit from real-time insights, enabling monitoring and optimization of performance. Applications range from predicting the economic impact of global crises to monitoring disease progression and customer behaviours.

5.7 Democratized AI:

The increased recognition and democratization of AI have added business value, facilitated easy access, and fostered innovation and creativity in media. This has resulted in the integration of AI into various work processes, making it more accessible and likable across different industries.

5.8 Personalization:

AI-driven personalization has yielded impressive results, prompting further research to optimize user experiences and business decision-making. This involves creating hyper-targeted and individualized customer experiences, enhancing the overall efficacy of personalized approaches in different sectors.

5.9 Automated Machine Learning (Auto ML):

One of the challenges in machine learning is the need for labelled data. Automated tools for data labelling help reduce dependence on manual annotation. The emergence of a labelling industry in cost-effective regions has been a response to the need for labelled data. However, concerns related to offshore labour are driving the industry to explore alternative methods. Advances in semi-supervised and self-supervised learning are reducing the reliance on manually labelled data. These approaches enable models to learn from partially labelled or unlabelled data, making the training process more efficient. Automation in selecting and fine-tuning neural network models is a key aspect of AutoML. By automating these processes, AI becomes more cost-effective, allowing for quicker deployment of solutions in the market.

5.10 Cybersecurity:

The commendable application of AI and ML in finance, banking, and fraud detection is a notable trend in Machine Learning. Ongoing advancements focus on real-time identification, warning systems, predictability, and neutralization of cyber threats to curb thefts and cybercrimes.

5.11 Bias and Mitigation:

Ensuring ethically sound AI is crucial for

expanded usage in law, healthcare, stock marketing, and other fields. Recent trends emphasize the development of measures, techniques, best practices, and ethical AI frameworks to address bias and mitigate potential ethical concerns.

5.12 Elevated Working:

The integration of human intelligence and AI to enhance efficiency and speed in various fields, including law, coding, education, research, and employment, is a highly anticipated and in-demand trend. The normalization and official incorporation of ML and AI are key objectives in this evolving landscape.

5.13 Advanced Vehicles and Intelligent Transport Systems:

Automated decision-making through Machine Learning is expected to improve sophisticated decision processes, increasing efficiency in environment recognition and control for safer rides. Traffic analysis efficiency is also anticipated to rise through current AI and ML trends.

5.14 Environmental Sustainability:

Addressing rising environmental concerns, AI is leveraged for **predictability, energy consumption optimization, pollution reduction, and maximizing the use of renewable energy sources**. Environmental sustainability is a prominent trend in AI for 2024, offering solutions for a greener and more sustainable future.

5.15 Robotics and Automation:

The widespread adoption of robotic and automated devices is transforming various industries, including **healthcare, logistics, housekeeping, manufacturing, and transportation**. This trend is driven by the possibilities of enhanced ease and efficiency in operations.

5.16 Legislation:

The increased use of AI, often in ethically questionable ways, has led to the need for effective laws to minimize harmful effects. Several countries, including the EU, the US, India, and the proposed bill in the UK, aim to regulate AI usage, striking a balance between positive and negative impacts.

5.17 Space Exploration:

Advancements in the space industry are incorporating AI to propel us further in exploration. AI trends in space exploration focus on analyzing habitable conditions, recognizing potential

exoplanets based on environmental factors, and commercializing space ventures.

6. CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTING AI and MACHINE LEARNING

Companies planning to introduce AI and ML to their functions are faced with unexpected challenges and encounters. These challenges include the identification of the right data, budget requirements, data, and privacy. Moreover, hiring the right people, integration with existing systems, and complex AI/ML algorithms also pose a roadblock for companies (12,13). Companies have decided to deploy AI and ML in their daily operations. But they have encountered various challenges.

Here are some of the challenges:

- **Finding the right data:** Acquiring high-quality, relevant, and sufficient data for training and testing machine learning models can be challenging. The usage of incomplete or biased datasets may lead to inaccurate or unfair predictions.
- **Budget requirements:** Implementing AI and ML systems can be costly due to expenses related to infrastructure, software, talent acquisition, and ongoing maintenance.
- **Data privacy issues:** Concerns around data privacy and compliance with regulations (such as GDPR) can hinder the collection, storage, and processing of sensitive information.
- **Hiring the right people:** There is a shortage of skilled professionals with expertise in AI and ML, including data scientists, machine learning engineers, and AI researchers.
- **Integration issues:** Integrating AI/ML solutions into existing workflows and systems can be complex and may require changes to existing processes.
- **Complexity of AI/ML Algorithms:** Implementing and understanding complex AI and ML algorithms can be challenging for non-experts, leading to difficulties in deployment and maintenance.

7. APPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY:

AI/ML is revolutionizing various facets of the pharmaceutical industry, from drug discovery to manufacturing and marketing (14,15,16). Here's a breakdown of how AI/ML is applied across different stages of the pharmaceutical pipeline:

7.1 Drug Discovery

➤ Target Validation and Choice:

Role: Identifies and validates drug targets (genes/proteins) and their relevance to diseases. **AI's Contribution** AI models analyse extensive datasets from genomics, proteomics, and clinical records to predict the efficacy and potential of drug targets. This includes evaluating genetic expressions and protein interactions.

➤ Screening of Compounds and Lead Optimization:

Role: Selects drug candidates through virtual screening and high-throughput screening. **AI's Contribution** AI facilitates virtual screening by leveraging large chemical databases and predicting the interaction between compounds and targets. This reduces the number of compounds needing experimental testing.

➤ Preclinical Research:

Role: Assesses safety and efficacy through laboratory tests. **AI's Contribution** AI helps process and analyse large volumes of biological data, revealing novel relationships and mechanisms of action. Techniques like clustering and ML algorithms can speed up the discovery of effective compounds.

➤ Clinical Research:

Role: Evaluates drug performance in human trials. **AI's Contribution** AI tools enhance patient condition recognition, predict drug outcomes, and optimize adherence. For instance, AI applications have improved medication adherence by up to 25% in some studies.

7.2 Drug Screening

Data resources are one of the fundamental elements using AI's role in drug screening including:

Target Identification: AI identifies potential drug targets.

Molecular Simulations: Simulates molecular interactions to predict properties.

Drug Property Predictions: AI predicts how drugs will perform based on molecular structures.

De Novo Drug Creation: AI aids in designing

new drug molecules from scratch. **Synthesis Route Generation:** AI proposes synthesis routes for new compounds. **Candidate Drug Prioritization:** AI prioritizes drug candidates for further development.

Data Resources for AI in Drug Discovery:

Databases: ChEMBL, ChemDB, DrugBank, PubChem.

Techniques: Delta Vina, neural graph fingerprints, AlphaFold, clustering, classification, regression analysis.

7.3 Drug Molecule Design

Role: Designing drug molecules traditionally involves extensive trial and error.

AI's Contribution: AI accelerates and refines molecular design by predicting successful synthesis routes, reducing byproducts, and lowering costs. AI-driven simulations and predictive models help in designing effective drug molecules with fewer iterations.

7.4 Pharmaceutical Production AI Applications:

Process Design and Scalability: AI identifies optimal processing parameters, reducing waste and development time.

Advance Process Control (ACP): AI integrates with real-time data to create efficient process controls and reduce downtime.

Trend Detection: AI analyzes customer feedback and complaint data to improve production quality.

7.5 Quality Assurance and Control

AI's Contribution:

Predictive Analytics: AI predicts variations that could affect product quality and safety.

Integration: AI enhances traditional quality control systems and supports automated data entry and analysis.

7.6 Designing Clinical Trials

AI's Contribution:

Design and Execution: AI aids in designing efficient clinical trials by analysing patient data and predicting trial outcomes. It improves patient selection and trial success rates, potentially reducing costs and timeframes.

Ethical Considerations: Ensures trials are conducted ethically while leveraging AI to optimize study design and execution.

7.7 Pharmaceutical Marketing AI Applications:

E-commerce: AI-driven marketing strategies can enhance targeting and customer engagement.

Market Expansion: AI tools can optimize marketing campaigns and improve market reach and effectiveness.

8. MARKET VALUE OF MACHINE LEARNING IN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRIES:

Marketing is the activity of increasing sales of a business's goods and services. Pharmaceutical companies will employ artificial intelligence (AI) for marketing by 2023. Additional benefits of using AI systems in the pharmaceutical industry include improved value propositions, effective resource allocation for higher market share gains, the capacity to maximize growth, and specialized sales and marketing information and channels. AI along with various computer software can be used in drug discovery. Each year, the pharmaceutical industry spends enormous sums of money on the research and development of new pharmaceuticals and chemicals. With a high probability of failure during clinical trials, they are faced with the problem of screening around 10,000 compounds in search of a single successful molecule. Developing only one medicinal molecule costs businesses \$2.6 billion on average. Pharmaceutical firms are using big data and artificial intelligence (AI) to design clinical trials to address these issues and minimize failure rates while also lowering R&D expenditures. With a 40% compound annual growth rate between 2017 and 2024, the market for artificial intelligence is expected to rise fast and reach \$5 billion by that time.

The AI in pharma market size is expected to see exponential growth in the next few years. It will grow to **\$5.62 billion in 2028 at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 28.5%**.

9. CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) are revolutionizing the pharmaceutical industry by speeding up drug discovery, enhancing clinical trial efficiency, and enabling personalized treatments. These technologies analyze vast amounts of data to uncover insights that streamline development and improve patient outcomes. However, challenges like data privacy and algorithm transparency need careful management. Overall, AI and ML hold great promise for transforming pharmaceutical practices, offering more effective, tailored healthcare solutions and accelerating the delivery of new therapies to patients. Their continued advancement will likely drive significant improvements in drug development and patient care.

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